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Attitude Towards Refuse Disposal Among Residents Of Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated attitude towards refuse disposal among residents of Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The population consisted of an estimated 3,480,000 adult residents in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The sample size for this study consisted of 300 residents in the four selected communities within the LGA using the multi-stage sampling procedure. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher. The reliability of this instrument was determined using the test-retest method with a reliability index of 0.78. The descriptive statistics of frequency, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. The result revealed a positive attitude (mean score 2.95) towards refuse disposal by residents of Port Harcourt metropolis. Also, there was a difference in attitude of the respondents based on gender. Based on these findings, it was recommended among others that government should develop and implement comprehensive education campaigns to raise awareness about proper refuse disposal methods, the environmental and health impacts of improper refuse management, and the benefits of sustainable practices such as recycling and composting. The local and state government, non-governmental organizations and other stakeholders should invest in expanding and upgrading refuse disposal facilities across Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Keywords: Refuse Disposal Attitude, Port Harcourt. Metropolis, Residents

INTRODUCTION

Proper refuse disposal is crucial to public health and environmental sustainability. In a global context, solid waste management is one of the most significant challenges, with increasing populations and industrialization in urban areas, which has resulted in increased solid waste generation. According to the World Bank (2018), an estimated 2.01 billion tonnes of solid waste is produced by cities annually; this number is expected to increase to 3.4 billion tonnes by 2050 with business-as-usual scenarios. Inefficient waste disposal practices can lead to environmental degradation, health hazards, and economic losses (Kaza et al., 2018).

In Nigeria, waste management remains a critical concern, especially in urban centers like Port Harcourt, Rivers State. Rapid urbanization, coupled with inadequate infrastructure, has exacerbated the challenge of refuse disposal (Ogbonna, Amangabara & Ekere, 2017). Port Harcourt, known as the "Garden City," has experienced significant environmental changes due to improper waste management, including blocked drainage systems, flooding, and the proliferation of diseases such as cholera and malaria (Eze, 2018).

Despite efforts by the Rivers State Waste Management Agency to address the issue, compliance with proper disposal practices remains inconsistent among residents.

Attitude refers to the feelings of likes and dislikes. Attitude emerges out of people's experiences which can be positive or negative. It is positive when a person develops a strong attraction to his likes, situations, objects, or other persons or groups. It is negative when the person develops a strong dislike for situations, objects, persons, groups, or other identifiable aspect of our environment. Oserenren (2016) stated that attitude is a mental and natural state of readiness organized through experience, exerting a directive or dynamic influences upon the individual's responses to all objects, events, and situations to which it is related. Anderson (2018) viewed attitude as a moderately intense emotion that predisposes individuals to respond consistently in a favourable or unfavourable manner when confronted with a particular object. The researcher further added that attitude is an important determinant of behaviour which substantially influences one's reactions in a wide variety of situations.

Alzoubi et al (2020) opined that attitude is how reality is perceived by the individual or group. Alzoubi et al also stated that it is learned and that attitude towards an object, group or individual develops with time upon when, where, and how it happens. In this study, an attitude refers to a feeling, emotion, or thinking that predisposes Port Harcourt residents, toward refuse disposal and how it affects others and the environment.

Public awareness and education are crucial components of effective waste management. Awareness campaigns that educate residents about the health and environmental impacts of improper waste disposal can significantly influence attitudes and practices. Schools, community groups, and media can play a vital role in disseminating information and encouraging positive behavior change. In Port Harcourt, there have been efforts by both government and non-governmental organizations to raise awareness about proper waste management. However, the reach and impact of these campaigns need to be assessed to ensure they are effective in changing public behavior.

The informal waste sector also plays a significant role in refuse management in many developing cities, including Port Harcourt. Informal waste collectors, often marginalized and working under precarious conditions, contribute to waste collection and recycling efforts. Recognizing and integrating the informal waste sector into the formal waste management system can enhance efficiency and provide social and economic benefits to these workers. Policies that support the informal sector and provide them with better working conditions and recognition can improve overall waste management.

Education significantly impacts attitudes toward refuse disposal. Individuals with higher educational qualifications are more likely to adopt proper waste management practices due to better awareness and understanding of environmental issues (Kaza et al., 2018). Occupation influences access to resources and attitudes toward waste management. For example, professionals or individuals in managerial roles are more likely to practice proper disposal methods compared to informal workers who may lack the resources or infrastructure (Chikeka, 2024; Eshete et al., 2023).

By addressing the challenges of inadequate infrastructure, enhancing public awareness and education, fostering community participation, and leveraging technology and regulatory frameworks, Port Harcourt can improve its refuse disposal practices. This, in turn, will contribute to better public health, environmental sustainability, and overall quality of life for its residents.

Based on this background, the researcher was motivated (by the indiscriminate and improper ways of disposing waste in the city). Therefore this study investigates the attitude towards refuse disposal among residents of Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Statement of the problem

The researcher has observed that improper refuse disposal poses a significant challenge to the environmental and public health landscape especially in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Despite the efforts by the Rivers State Waste Management Agency (RIWAMA) and other stakeholders to address these issues, compliance with proper disposal practices remains inconsistent among residents, the city continues to grapple with issues such as indiscriminate dumping, clogged waterways, and increased incidence of

waste-related diseases. Lack of compliance with proper disposal guidelines raises questions about residents' attitude towards waste management, and the factors influencing their practices.

Previous studies have identified that urbanization and population growth contribute to increased waste generation in Port Harcourt. However, there is a paucity of research that focuses on the behavioral and attitudinal dimensions of waste disposal among residents. Understanding these dimensions is essential for addressing the root causes of improper waste disposal and improving existing waste management systems. Thus, this study investigates the attitude towards refuse disposal among residents of Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study investigates attitude towards refuse disposal among residents of Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. It also focused on the following specific objectives:

1. to determine the attitude towards refuse disposal among residents of Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.
2. to determine the attitude towards refuse disposal among residents of Port Harcourt Metropolis based on gender.

Research Questions

The following research questions are formulated to guide the study

1. What is the attitude towards refuse disposal among residents of Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State?
2. What is the attitude towards refuse disposal among residents of Port Harcourt Metropolis based on gender?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are postulated to guide the study.

1. There is no significant difference in the attitude towards refuse disposal among residents of Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State based on gender.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The descriptive survey design was employed in this study. According to Nwankwo (2013), this design allows the researcher to collect from a sample drawn from a larger population and describing the characteristics and features of such sample without manipulating the independent variables. Hence, the current study used this design because the researcher sought to draw data from a sample that was drawn from a population of residents of Port Harcourt metropolis.

The population of the study consisted of all adult residents in Port Harcourt metropolis with an estimated population of 3,480,000 (National Population Commission, 2024).

The sample size for the study was 300 residents in the four selected communities within Port Harcourt metropolis. The residents were selected using multi-stage sampling procedure;

Firstly, the metropolis was stratified into two LGAs (Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor).

Secondly, simple random sampling technique was used to select two communities from each local government area.

Lastly at stage three, purposive sampling technique was used to select respondents who are easily accessible. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled "Attitude towards Refuse Disposal among Residents in Port Harcourt Metropolis Questionnaire (ARDRPHMQ)". The questionnaire was designed in sections: Section A contained the demographic variables of the respondent while Section B contained the items on the various constructs measured. The response option to ascertain respondents' attitude towards refuse disposal was on a 4-point Likert scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The criterion mean was 2.50.

The reliability of the instrument was determined using test-retest method with a reliability coefficient of 0.78. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyse the data on the attitude towards refuse disposal.

While z-test was used to analyse the hypothesis at the .05 level of significance. The quantitative data was presented in tables, charts and graphs

RESULTS

Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Table 1 Frequency distribution on gender of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	125	42
Female	175	58
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Fig. 1 – Gender of the respondents

Table 1 presented above shows that 125 respondents which represent 42% of the sample are males while 175 respondents which represent 58% are females.

Table 2 - Mean and standard deviation analysis on attitude towards refuse disposal among residents of Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State N = 300

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	S.D	Remarks
1	People dispose of refuse properly in my community	32	42	164	62	2.14	0.86	Negative
2	Putting refuse into refuse containers is the responsibility of everybody.	104	158	12	26	3.13	0.84	Positive
3	Proper refuse disposal is important to prevent disease	85	139	21	55	2.85	1.03	Positive
4	Government should create more awareness to promote proper refuse disposal.	157	99	16	28	2.85	1.02	Positive
5	Penalties should be imposed on individuals that dispose refuse improperly	79	179	31	11	3.09	0.71	Positive
6	Refuse is one of the environmental problems that need immediate attention.	111	161	17	11	3.24	0.71	Positive
7	Reusing plastic bags for storing or drinking water bottles can reduce waste from source.	81	194	18	7	3.17	0.63	Positive
8	Recycling is the best refuse disposal method because it saves our natural resources.	123	151	6	20	3.26	0.79	Positive
9	Refuse collected is disposed into water bodies	74	200	11	15	3.11	0.68	Positive
10	Burning of refuse is better than open dumping	67	214	9	10	3.13	0.61	Positive
11	Local authorities are doing enough to manage refuse disposal.	51	72	141	36	2.46	0.91	Negative
12	People have adequate education on proper refuse disposal	92	81	89	38	2.75	1.02	Positive
13	Proper refuse disposal is the responsibility of both the government and individuals.	105	178	10	7	3.27	0.63	Positive
Grand Mean						2.95	0.80	Positive

From the data presented in table 2 above, items 25 had its mean as 2.14 while item 35 had a mean of 2.46. The mean of the items are below the criterion mean of 2.50 and showed that many of the respondents disagreed with the statements that: ‘people dispose of refuse properly in their communities’ and also that ‘local authorities are doing enough to manage refuse disposal.’ This was clear that local authorities were not doing enough to manage refuse disposal and that many persons do not dispose refuse properly in the communities. Most of the responses had the criterion mean of above 2.50. On the whole, a grand mean of 2.95 was realized against the criterion mean of 2.50. Hence, since this was above the criterion mean, it was agreed generally that residents had a positive attitude towards refuse disposal in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the attitude of residents of Port Harcourt Metropolis towards refuse disposal based on demographic variables (gender).

Table 3 – Independent t-test analysis on the attitude of residents of Port Harcourt Metropolis towards refuse disposal based on gender.

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. D	df	T	Sig	Result
Attitude to Refuse Disposal	Male	125	50.13	9.83	288	-3.11	0.002	Significant
	Female	175	54.19	11.98				

Table 3 above showed mean score of residents attitude based on gender, it was reviewed that female resident had a more positive attitude (54.19) than their male counterpart (50.13). when this was subjected to hypothesis test, the calculated t-value was -0.311 while the sig value was 0.002. Hence, since sig ($p=0.002<0.05$) is less than the alpha of 0.05 at 288 degrees of freedom., the null hypothesis was rejected meaning that there is a significant difference in the attitude of male and female residents of Port Harcourt Metropolis towards refuse disposal.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study revealed that residents of Port Harcourt metropolis had a positive attitude towards refuse disposal. This means that residents of the area did not like dirty and unsanitary environment littered with refuse. This finding is in tandem with study by Kaithery and Karunakaran (2019) in a rural area of Northern Kerala. That showed that majority of the participants had positive attitude towards household refuse management and that continuous awareness programmes should be conducted on safe refuse disposal to sustain the supervision of household refuse management. The findings of the study is in constrast to that of Eneji, Eneji, Ngoka and Abang (2017) who examined the attitude towards refuse management and disposal methods and the health status of Cross River State, Nigeria and found that the residents of Calabar South had very negative attitude towards refuse management and disposal due to indiscriminate disposal of refuse, the cause of this finding could have been as a result of the strict government policies against poor refuse disposal system. Policies like high selling of waste bin by local government area councils, application of high fine rates, seizure of properties as well as closure of business with dirty environment may have all contributed to this.

The hypothesis also revealed that there was a significant difference in the attitude of respondent on refuse disposal based on gender. This means that demographic characteristics influence attitudes towards refuse disposal. It could also be that different groups have varying levels of concern, awareness, or motivation regarding proper refuse disposal. The findings here is not surprising because peoples attitude towards something may differ as a result of their demographic backgrounds like the level of educational they have, their gender etc. It could also be that policy makers have been considering demographic differences when implementing waste management strategies. It could also be that certain gender like women may be more concerned about health impacts while men may prioritize convenience and profit.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it is certain that the attitude towards refuse disposal vary significantly based on gender. Hence, demographic factors play a crucial role in shaping attitudes and practices related to refuse disposal. Therefore, targeted interventions and education campaigns should be designed to address specific demographic groups. Residents are typically aware of the visible consequences of improper refuse disposal, such as blocked drainage systems leading to flooding or the spread of diseases due to unsanitary conditions. However, there is a limited understanding of the broader environmental impacts, such as the long-term effects of plastic waste on marine ecosystems or the role of waste management in

mitigating climate change. However, despite this positive disposition, there is a noticeable discrepancy between what residents know and believe about refuse disposal and how they actually behave.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. government and relevant stakeholders should carry out aggressive awareness and sensitization programs that can affect the attitude of the resident positively towards refuse disposal.
2. The local and state government, non-governmental organizations and other stakeholders should invest in expanding and upgrading refuse disposal facilities across Port Harcourt Metropolis. This includes providing more public refuse bins, establishing recycling centers, and ensuring regular refuse collection services, particularly in underserved and low-income areas.
3. Government should enforce existing refuse management regulations more rigorously by increasing penalties for non-compliance and conducting regular inspections and monitoring of refuse disposal practices. Authorities should also improve communication about the regulations to ensure residents understand their responsibilities and the consequences of violations.

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